

RESOURCES

NEW RESOURCES IN AMERICAN STUDIES FILM and HISTORY

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The recent release of the feature films *13 Days* (2001) and *Pearl Harbor* (2001), and the critical reaction to their historical veracity, resuscitates debates over the role of film and video as sources of historical and cultural understanding. As Michael Sturma pointed out in the last issue of *AJAS*, the meanings gained from film inform students' historical insights in multiple ways. In 1988 media theorist Alan Rosenthal argued that documentary film 'has become a major- possibly the most important- means for learning about the past. In an age when reading is in decline, the documentary- much more than theater, newspapers, or feature films- may well be the only serious access people have to history once they have left school.' (Alan Rosenthal, ed., *New Challenges for Documentary*, University of California Press, Berkeley, 1988, p. 426). Rosenthal's perceptions concerning the importance of documentary film to historical understanding were updated recently with reference to the role of fictional films in the same process. The insight appeared in what was otherwise an unlikely context- the controversy surrounding history lecturer Joseph Ellis of Mount Holyoke College who falsely claimed to his classes that he was a Vietnam veteran. In writing of the issue, the *LA Times* ('For Historian's Students, a Hard Lesson on Lying', 22 June, 2001) quoted Jim Sleeper, lecturer in journalism at Yale, who argued that today's students 'learn [much of their history] through fictional films such as 'Pearl Harbor' and 'JFK'. Precisely at times such as these...students need good teachers to help them sort fact from fiction.' Accepting the various assertions concerning the importance of film to understanding history and culture, what follows immediately below are details of recent sources capable of informing the use of documentary film in teaching.

Described as 'public television's resident historian' (G. Edgerton, *Journal of American Culture*, vol. 18, no. 1, spring 1995, pp. 1-12), Ken Burns has compiled a lengthy filmography which includes a number of notable television documentary series. Burns' work, as in the well-known series *The Civil War*, for example, mixes archival sources (including film, photographs, letters, and memoir) with talking heads in a way which accomplishes something most documentary filmmakers aim to achieve: it renders the subject interesting and- to use a word not often deployed in documentary theory- entertaining. The combination of an interesting topic, and solid and informed research, presented in an entertaining manner, makes Burns' documentaries useful tools for teaching US history and culture.

Burns' recent ten-hour series *Jazz*, which screened on the Public Broadcasting System in the US during January 2001, examines the musical form from its roots to its current deployments. As one reviewer acknowledges, '[s]ome will view the series as musically conservative, failing to explore the more adventurous styles of Avant-Garde and Free Jazz...Others will criticize the scant coverage of jazz after 1961, with fusion only being mentioned in relation to Miles Davis' later work, and Charles Mingus only receiving a very short biography.' However, as the same reviewer points out, '*Jazz* is an audacious undertaking that will successfully introduce jazz and jazz history to the uninitiated...' (online review by R. Lankford at www.documentaryfilms.net). In the US the series has become a site of debate over issues of race and has generated or renewed discussion of a musical form that some may have felt had been overlooked in the proliferation of contemporary musical styles such as rap, hip hop, and acid house. The series has been reviewed in the *New York Review of Books*, see D. Hajdu, 'Not Quite All That Jazz', *New York Review of Books*, vol. 48, no. 2, 8 February, 2001, pp. 31-33.

Burns' own web site offers details of his films. The web site announces that his next project is a documentary on the life of Mark Twain to be aired on PBS during 2001. See <www.documentaryfilms.net/kenburns> Burns has produced the television series: *Baseball*, *The Civil War*, *Congress*, *Empire of the Air: The Men Who Made Radio*, *Frank Lloyd Wright*, *Lewis and Clark: The Journey of the Corps of Discovery*, *Statue of Liberty*, *Thomas Hart Benton*, *Thomas Jefferson*, *The West*, and *Not For Ourselves Alone: The Story of Elizabeth Cady Stanton and Susan B. Anthony*, the subject of an extended interview with Burns in the *San Francisco Examiner Magazine*, 7 November, 1999, pp. 8-12, 20-24.

Many of these series are supported by informative web pages which include information on the purchase of the videos. The pages accompanying *Lewis and Clark*, for example, include sections on the Corps of Discovery, Native Americans, an archive of primary sources, comments by historians, a forum with Burns, and classroom activities. The pages are located on the PBS site at <www.pbs.org>.

A number of Burns' films have featured in PBS's *The American Experience* series. Described by the PBS web site as 'television's longest-running, most-watched history series' *The American Experience* debuted in 1988 and has to date produced over 125 programs (most of which can be purchased through the web site). Recent programs (screened in the US in early 2001) include *Abraham and Mary Lincoln: A House Divided*, *Houdini*, *Meltdown at Three Mile Island*, and *Scottsboro: An American Tragedy*. Many of the programs and series are accompanied by dedicated pages within the PBS web site. The pages supporting the series *Race for the Superbomb*, for example, include among other features,

a program description, enhanced transcript, extended interviews with the program participants, a bibliography, a list of articles and web sites relating to the topic, and copies of primary source documents.

The PBS site includes a range of relevant programs beyond those included in *The American Experience*, among them the ten-hour series *An American Love Story*. The series details the lives of Bill Sims and Karen Wilson, a black man married to a white woman, and their thirty-year struggle against racial prejudice and societal stereotypes. The filmmaker, Jennifer Fox, documented the couple over a period of eighteen months, amassing over 1,000 hours of footage. Details of the series are located at <www.pbs.org/weblab/lovestories/>. An interview with Jennifer Fox is located at <www.documenter.com/issue031>.

Other web sites useful for the study of US culture include the Vanderbilt Television Archives <<http://tvnews.vanderbilt.edu/>> , a unit of Vanderbilt University, Nashville. It abstracts nightly news broadcasts from various television stations, including CNN, ABC, CBC, and NBC. The archive is now in its fourth decade of operation and holds in excess of 23,000 network evening news broadcasts (replete with advertisements). In addition to the taped nightly newscasts the archive holds more than 8,000 hours of news-related programming, including special reports; presidential speeches and press conferences; election night reports; and coverage of national and international events, such as the Watergate hearings and the Gulf War. Copies of videotapes from the archive's collections are loaned to individuals throughout the world. The archive produces a monthly guide to the collections.

The Prelinger Archives, a private corporation committed to providing public access to its collections, includes the Internet Moving Images Archive, which offers digitised versions of over 1,000 key films for free downloading. <www.archive.org/movies/>

Recent publications on film/television and US history and culture (Listed by author)

John Bodnar, 'Saving Private Ryan and Postwar Memory in America', *American Historical Review*, vol. 106, no. 3, June 2001, pp. 805-817.

Natalie Z. Davis, *Slaves on Screen: Film and Historical Vision.*, Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Mass., 2000. Davis examines the representation of slaves in five films, including *Armistad* and *Beloved*.

G. Edgerton and P. Rollins, eds., *Television Histories: Shaping Collective Memory in the Media Age.*, The University Press of Kentucky, Lexington, 2001.

Geoff Eley, 'Finding the People's War: Film, British Collective Memory, and World War II', *American Historical Review*, vol. 106, no. 3, June 2001, pp. 818-838.

Willem Hesling, 'The Past as Story: the Narrative Structure of Historical Films', *European Journal of Cultural Studies*, vol. 4, no. 2, 2001, pp. 189-205. (Includes references to *Saving Private Ryan*, *Forrest Gump*, and *JFK*, among other films).

Del Jacobs, *Revisioning Film Traditions: the Pseudo-Documentary and the Neo-Western.*, Edwin Mellen Press, Lewiston, New York, 2000. A curious book, the first half of which examines 'pseudo' or mock documentaries (*David Holzman's Diary*, *Bob Roberts*, and *Zelig*) and, in the second half Jacobs examines the histories of neo-Westerns such as *Hearts of the West*, *The Grey Fox*, and *Lone Star*.

Catherine G. Kodat, 'Saving Private Property: Steven Spielberg's American DreamWorks', *Representations*, no. 71, Summer 2000, pp. 77-105.

Laura Marks, *The Skin of the Film: Intercultural Cinema, Embodiment, and the Senses.* Duke University Press, Durham, 2000. Examines the ways in which film can evoke physical awareness of touch and smell. The memories produced by such sensations are, Marks argues, vital links to home for people living in diaspora from their culture of origin. Marks draws on Deleuze and others to explain how intercultural cinema represents embodied experience in a transnational world.

Kathleen Moran and Michael Rogin, "'What's the Matter with Capra?': *Sullivan's Travels* and the Popular Front', *Representations*, no. 71, Summer 2000, pp. 106-134.

Christopher Probst, 'One Nation Under Siege', *American Cinematographer*, vol. 82, no. 5, 2001, pp. 36-49. (On *Pearl Harbor*).

P. Rabinowitz, 'Medium Uncool: Women Shoot Back: Feminism, Film and 1968- a Curious Documentary', *Science and Society*, vol. 65, no. 1, Spring 2001, pp. 72-98.

N. Sy, 'Recounting "History": Documentary as Women's Cinema', *Asian Journal of Women's Studies*, vol. 7, no. 1, 2001, pp. 80-110.

Jay Winter, 'Film and the Matrix of Memory', *American Historical Review*, vol. 106, no. 3, June 2001, pp. 857-864.

Denise Youngblood, 'A War Remembered: Soviet Films of the Great Patriotic War', *American Historical Review*, vol. 106, no. 3, June 2001, pp. 838-856.

The US journal *Film and History* publishes essays which deal with aspects of the connection between (mainly fictional feature) films and history. Articles from past issues include Robert Allen, 'Historiography and the Teaching of Film'; Warren Susman, 'History and Film: Artifact and Experience'; Leger Grindon, 'Drama and Spectacle as Historical Explanation in the Fiction Film'; and David Mould and Charles Berg, 'Fact and Fantasy in the Films of World War I'. Forthcoming theme issues include The Cold War (2001), Holocaust (2002), The American West (2003), and Latin America (2004). The journal maintains a website <www2.h-net.msu.edu/~filmhis> that contains information on the journal and related publications. The site includes links to related resources on the Web.

General Resources

Books

(Listed by book title)

Abraham Lincoln and the Forge of National Memory. By Barry Schwartz, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago, 2000. Schwartz has published widely on the topic of national memory in the US. This book examines the changes to the popular image of Lincoln during the six decades after his assassination.

America Divided: The Civil War of the 1960s. By Maurice Isserman and Michael Kazin, Oxford University Press, New York, 2000. An interpretative survey of the decade of the 1960s that concentrates on developments in domestic politics, tending to downplay the place and role of cultural phenomena (there is only one reference to the counterculture of hippies). Curiously, in a work which otherwise examines a range of organised political protest, the book includes only one brief reference to the activities of Vietnam Veterans Against the War.

American Studies in a Moment of Danger. By George Lipsitz, University of Minnesota Press, Minneapolis, 2001. Lipsitz examines the connections between notions of 'national knowledge' and American studies. He draws on popular music, paintings, and cinema to argue that American studies has been shaped by the social movements of the 1930s, 1960s, and 1980s which, in turn, have reworked the concept of the nation in an era of globalisation.

Another American Century? The United States and the World after 2000. By Nicholas Guyatt, Zed Books, London and New York, 2000. Howard Zinn calls Guyatt's book 'a succinct, bold and penetrating critique of the triumphalist

ideology which insists on American domination'. Guyatt draws on the experiences of the past decade to outline the effects and consequences of America's continued global economic, political, and cultural power.

The Big Tomorrow: Hollywood and the Politics of the American Way. By Lary May, University of Chicago Press, Chicago, 2000. Spanning the period from the Depression to the early 1950s, May studies the particular vision projected by Hollywood during the period. The author emphasises the populist and egalitarian worldview of an industry that impacted in crucial ways on politics and society.

Conspiracy Culture: From Kennedy to the X Files. By Peter Knight, Routledge, New York, 2001. Traces the development of conspiracy culture from the 1960s counter-cultural suspicions of authority to the paranoid attitude of the 1990s.

Conspiracy Theories: Secrecy and Power in American Culture. By Mark Fenster, University of Minnesota Press, Minneapolis, 1999. Conspiracy theories in the US involving figures as diverse as Marx, the Pope, JFK, Howard Hughes, and Clinton are the subject of Fenster's book.

Cop Knowledge: Police Power and Cultural Narrative in Twentieth-Century America. By Christopher Wilson, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago, 2000. Wilson draws on range of sources, including popular fiction, film, and tabloid newspapers, to examine the place of the 'cop' in American cultural narratives and the effects of those narratives on law-enforcement strategies and urban politics.

Dancing at the Devil's Party: Essays on Poetry, Politics, and the Erotic. By Alicia Ostriker, The University of Michigan Press, Ann Arbor, 2000. A volume in the series 'Poets on Poetry'. Ostriker discusses Whitman, eroticism in the poetry of Elizabeth Bishop and Sharon Olds, the poetry of Maxine Kumin and Lucille Clifton. The final essay is on "'Howl'" Revisited'.

Immigration and Race: New Challenges for American Democracy. Edited by Gerald Jaynes, Yale University Press, New Haven, 2000. This book contains ten essays which examine the impact, notably economic, of immigration policy decisions on African Americans.

To Lead the Free World: American Nationalism and the Cultural Roots of the Cold War. By John Fousek, The University of North Carolina Press, Chapel Hill, 2000. In this cultural history of the origins of the Cold War, Fousek argues that American nationalism provided the ideological cement for the broad consensus that supported US foreign policy in the Cold War era. From a close

reading of a range of texts- including presidential speeches, popular magazines, labour union debates, cartoon images- Fousek demonstrates how traditional ideas about national greatness, providential mission, and manifest destiny influenced postwar public culture and helped shape US foreign policy during the 1950s.

Modernization as Ideology: American Social Science and 'Nation Building' in the Kennedy Era. By Michael E. Latham, The University of North Carolina Press, Chapel Hill, 2000. A volume in the 'New Cold War History' series, edited by John Lewis Gaddis, this book examines the ways in which ideas derived from and circulating within theories of social science helped shape American foreign policy during the Kennedy administration. Latham contends that during America's Cold War the concept of modernisation moved out of academia to become a motivating ideology behind policy decision-making at the governmental level. Latham argues that the core assumptions of modernisation theory influenced the Kennedy administration's Alliance for Progress with Latin America, the creation of the Peace Corps, and the strategic hamlet program in Vietnam.

National Imaginaries, American Identities: the Cultural Work of American Iconography. Edited by Larry Reynolds and Gordon Hutner, Princeton University Press, Princeton, New Jersey, 2000. The essays collected here examine the ways in which visual texts from the American Revolution to the present construct a sense of national identity.

Post-Nationalist American Studies. By John C. Rowe, University of California Press, Berkeley, 2000. A series of essays which examine various themes connected to the 'post-national' in American studies, particularly, the internationalisation of American studies, and with it an inclusion of multicultural viewpoints. In various ways the essays respond to a call by Jane Desmond and Virginia Dominguez in *American Quarterly* for a 'critical internationalism' within American studies which would admit the work of non-US scholars.

Racialized Politics: The Debate about Racism in America. Edited by David Sears, Jim Sidanius, Lawrence Bobo, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago, 2000. A collection of essays in which sociologists, political scientists, and psychologists examine current debates surrounding the sources of racism in America.

Race and Reunion: the Civil War in American Memory. By David Blight, Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Mass., 2001. Blight examines the processes of remembering and forgetting which accompanied the Civil War, arguing that the US 'healed' from the Civil War in ways which denied justice.

Reflections in Black: A History of Black Photographers, 1840 to the Present. By Deborah Willis and Robin Kelley, Norton, New York, 2000. Willis, a curator of photography at the Smithsonian, has selected nearly 600 photographs by black photographers. Robin Kelly of the history department at New York University has written an accompanying text.

The Second Century of Cinema: The Past and Future of the Moving Image. By Wheeler Winston Dixon, State University of New York Press, Albany, 2000. Dixon investigates the impact of digital filmmaking effects on the production and exhibition of films in the twenty-first century. He argues that Hollywood will remain culturally and economically dominant although, somewhat paradoxically, he also foresees, within Hollywood's continued dominance, the emergence in the next century of cinema a cross-cultural and international 'democracy of images'.

Star Authors: Literary Celebrity in America. By Joe Moran, Pluto Press, London, 2000. Moran examines the ways in which publishers, the media, and authors themselves construct literary celebrity. The authors discussed include Salinger, Pynchon, Updike, Toni Morrison, and Jay McInerney.

Tabloid Culture: Trash Taste, Popular Power, and the Transformation of American Television. By Kevin Glynn, Duke University Press, Durham, 2000. Glynn analyses the development- with Reaganism as a prime context- and current deployment of the 'tabloidization' of US television. His study includes television talk shows, and forms of television 'infotainment'. Glynn is a member of the American Studies Department of the University of Canterbury, Christchurch.

Vietnam and Other American Fantasies. By H. Bruce Franklin, University of Massachusetts Press, Amherst, 2000. Chapters include 'The Antiwar Movement We Are Supposed to Forget'; 'Burning Illusions: the Napalm Campaign'; 'The Vietnam War and the Culture Wars'; and 'The Vietnam War as American Science Fiction and Fantasy'. Franklin opens his book with a brief essay, 'On "Differing Perceptions of Reality"' in which he discusses his sacking by Stanford University in 1971 for delivering speeches against the university's involvement with the Vietnam War.

Electronic Resources

Although the dot.com bubble has burst there are an increasing number of useful web sites for American Studies scholars. These resources can be grouped in two types: 1) *Indexes, Search Engines and Subject lists*, and 2) *Content Rich sites*.

Indexes, Search Engines and Subject Lists

Of the current search engines www.google.com has been found to produce the best-focussed lists of results. Those in search of images to illustrate lectures will probably find www.altavista.com, which has a specific images search feature, the most helpful.

The History Cooperative (<http://www.historycoop.org/>) makes the current issues of major History journals such as *Journal of American History* and *American Historical Review* available online. Libraries that subscribe to the hard copy can arrange for institutional access. The site has a useful search engine.

JSTOR (www.jstor.org/jstor/) is an electronic archive of back issues (2-5 years) of journals. The archive offers searchable full text of journals such as *JAH* and *American Quarterly*. Although of Australian and New Zealand universities only ANU, Auckland, Monash, Queensland, and Sydney subscribe to the service others may be able to use the search engine.

Project Muse (<http://muse.jhu.edu/muse.html>) is another subscription based online journal venture with a search engine. *American Quarterly* is among its list of over 100 current journals.

The H-Amstdy (<http://www2.h-net.msu.edu/~amstdy/>) and indeed all the H-Net lists have fully searchable logs. These can be very useful for locating sources on given topics or simply recovering a post of groups of posts you might have previously seen.

Of the many web sites that offer lists of American Studies Resources Richard P. Horowitz's (<http://twist.lib.uiowa.edu/rhorwitz/>) is perhaps the most user friendly.

A rougher list of my own can be found at: http://www.fas.nus.edu.sg/asc/web_resources.htm

The Voice of the Shuttle: Web Page for Humanities Research (<http://vos.ucsb.edu>) contains an extensive list of web resources including many for US History and Literature.

George Mason University's History Matters web site (<http://historymatters.gmu.edu/>) part of the Center for History and New Media (<http://chnm.gmu.edu/>) has recently been updated and includes recent syllabi and other resources.

Content Rich Sites

Cultural Readings: Colonization and Print in the Americas (<http://www.library.upenn.edu/special/gallery/kislak/index/cultural.html>) is an online exhibition from the University of Pennsylvania Library that examines the link between colonization and the production of texts by Europeans as they sought to comprehend what they had wrought.

The Internet Archive (<http://www.archive.org/index.html>) is an important collection of Internet based sources that would otherwise disappear. For instance, the web sites of the US 2000 and 1996 Presidential elections are archived here. Also available at this web site is the aforementioned Perlinger Archives (<http://www.archive.org/movies/>) a collection of about 1,000 ephemeral films. Titles include *California State Fair* (1913), *Century 21 Calling* (1964), and *Duck and Cover* (1951). The films are all downloadable at no cost.

The Literature and Culture of the American 1950s (<http://www.english.upenn.edu/~afilreis/50s/home.html>) brings together a diverse set of resources on that decade including Mickey Mantle's FBI file, and key lines from *Rebel Without a Cause*.

Michigan State University Library's Digital Sources Center (<http://digital.lib.msu.edu>) has a range of material from its Special Collections on topics such as American Radicalism (including eight SDS pamphlets), Birth Control, and Sunday School Books.

The National Archives (<http://www.nara.gov/exhall/exhibits.html>) offers a wide array of documents and images from the obvious (Declaration of Independence and the Constitution) to the bizarre (When Nixon Met Elvis).

The 1920s (<http://www.louisville.edu/~kprayb01/1920s.html>) offers something similar for that earlier decade but is a little more complex to navigate.

The Online Speech Bank site (<http://www.americanrhetoric.com/speechbank.htm>) offers text and audio of sermons and speeches. Includes Martin Luther King's "I Have a Dream."

The US History and Politics Out Loud (<http://www.hpol.org/>) has audio files including Franklin Roosevelt and Kennedy's inauguration speeches.

The Whitney Museum (<http://whitney.artmuseum.net/tac.html>) has a flashy online exhibition of the American Century.

The Women of Color Web (<http://www.hsph.harvard.edu/grhf/WoC/>) contains analysis and discussion as well as a teaching tools section.

Finally, there are several inflation calculators available on the web, which are handy for both research and student assignments. The Inflation Calculator (<http://www.westegg.com/inflation/>) and Economic History Services (<http://eh.net/ehresources/howmuch/dollarq.php>) sites both convert US dollar figures.